

THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF GREEN ENERGY IN SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This article discusses the concept of "Green Energy," its significance, and its role in the sustainable development of the national economy. The paper also includes information about the newly launched and under-construction power plants in various regions of Azerbaijan and new production areas that are economically and ecologically important. It is noted that the effective use of alternative, or rather renewable, energy sources and proper waste management contributes to the conservation of natural resources and energy.

Keywords: energy, power plant, economic development, ecology

Introduction

"Green energy" refers to energy sources that have minimal impact on the environment and are also renewable. It is derived from natural resources such as the sun, wind, water, and other renewable or non-exhaustible resources. One of the primary goals of "green energy" is to reduce the use of fossil fuels (natural gas, oil, coal) in energy production, thereby preventing and minimizing atmospheric pollution and climate change. Since "green energy" sources are renewable, they ensure long-term sustainability in energy production. Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, water, geothermal, and wave energy help reduce dependence on fossil fuels, making them economically beneficial as well.

Main Body

In the modern era, green energy constitutes a significant part of the changing energy economy in Azerbaijan. As is well known, Azerbaijan has great potential for the development of green energy. In recent years, the effective use of solar, wind, and other alternative energy sources has increased in importance for the sustainable development of the country's economy. It is no coincidence that in the "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development" approved by President Ilham Aliyev, the fifth priority is "Clean environment and the country of green growth." The document emphasizes the implementation of eco-friendly technologies, waste recycling, and the restoration of polluted areas, as well as the widespread adoption of "green" technologies. Steps are being taken to improve the quality of green energy infrastructure in Azerbaijan. Hosting the COP29 conference demonstrates Azerbaijan's international role in climate change discussions. Hosting this conference further underscores the country's commitment to climate change and energy issues.

The recycling process established in Azerbaijan contributes to the dynamic development of the economy, the expansion of competitive industrial product manufacturing, and the improvement of ecological conditions. In order to create favorable conditions for en-

trepreneurs and potential investors in the field of recycling, the Balakhani Industrial Park was established by a decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 28, 2011. The creation of this 10.15-hectare park aims to expand the production of competitive industrial products based on high technologies, develop the non-oil sector, including "green" economy, increase employment in the production sector, and improve the ecological situation in Baku and surrounding areas. In the implementation of the "Comprehensive Action Plan for Improving the Ecological Situation in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2006-2010", the Waste Incineration Plant in Baku, with an annual capacity of 500,000 tons of household waste and 10,000 tons of medical waste, which started operations in 2012, produces 231.5 million kWh of electricity from the incineration of waste. This plant is considered the largest facility in Eastern Europe and the CIS region in terms of production capacity [1]. In relation to waste neutralization and sorting, the Balakhani City Waste Disposal Facility, handed over to the "Clean City" OJSC in 2009, uses modern technical equipment to neutralize waste, and the gas emitted during the process is also used to generate electricity. In order to develop the business of sorting and recycling household waste, the "Clean City" OJSC's Solid Waste Sorting Plant, which has a capacity to process 200,000 tons of waste annually, reduces the overall volume of waste by sorting and creates a cheap raw material base for the Balakhani Industrial Park. The operation of this plant contributes to the efficient management of waste, resulting in savings in natural resources and energy. In the territories liberated during the 44-day Patriotic War, large-scale restoration and construction works are being carried out. In line with the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated May 3, 2021, regarding the creation of a "green energy" zone in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan, the involvement of an international consulting company was planned. In this regard, cooperation was initiated with Japan's TEPCO company, and a relevant Concept Paper was developed. The purpose of this concept is to provide the region with ecologically clean

green energy using the high renewable energy potential available in the liberated territories and to explore the prospects of applying environmentally clean and energy-efficient green technologies, while making proposals. In this context, energy demand models for the territories were developed by applying various scenarios. Within the framework of the restoration of electricity generation capacities in the liberated territories, four hydroelectric power plants (HPPs) with a total capacity of 20.2 MW (Gulabird HPP-8 MW, Suqovushan-1 HPP-4.8 MW, Suqovushan-2 HPP-3 MW, Kalbajar-1 HPP-4.4 MW) have already been commissioned in Lachin, Kalbajar, and Suqovushan. In addition, the construction of the Nadirxanli HPP with a capacity of 8.8 MW, Ashagi Veng HPP with 8.6 MW, Merik HPP with 3.5 MW, Agbulaq-1 HPP with 14.2 MW, and Agbulaq-2 HPP with 14.8 MW has been completed. At the same time, two hydroelectric power plants are being built on the Araz River in the Jabrayil region, with a total capacity of 140 MW (100 MW "Khudaferin", 40 MW "Kiz Qalasi") for the Azerbaijani side. Additionally, the construction of the Tekekaya HPP (7.7 MW), Agchay HPP (3 MW), Chaykend HPP (5 MW) in Kalbajar, Sheylanli HPP (4 MW), Ashagi Malibeyli HPP (3.1 MW) in Lachin, and Qozlukorpu HPP (14.7 MW) in Agdere is currently underway. The total expected annual electricity generation capacity of these six HPPs is 110 million kWh, which will save 24 million cubic meters of gas and prevent the emission of 44,000 tons of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. Furthermore, the planned construction of a 100 MW wind power station in the Lachin/Kalbajar area will make an additional contribution to the creation of the "Green Energy Zone" in the liberated territories. On December 18, 2020, a supply agreement was signed between Azerenerji OJSC and Italy's Ansaldo Energia in the field of mutual cooperation. According to the agreement, the supply of equipment for the 110 kV substations being constructed in the Agdam, Fuzuli, Kalbajar, and Gubadli regions is planned. On June 3, 2021, an implementation agreement was signed between the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan and BP to assess and implement a 240 MW solar power plant project in the Zangilan/Ce-brail region. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, an integral part of the Republic of Azerbaijan, also has significant energy potential and is a key source of "green energy." As noted by President Ilham Aliyev, the Karabakh, Eastern Zangezur, and Nakhchivan regions have been declared "green energy zones." In the modern era, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has made significant progress in the energy sector, as in other areas. Alongside new hydroelectric power plants, solar and wind power plants have also been commissioned in the autonomous republic. The use of alternative and renewable energy sources in the Nakhchivan

Autonomous Republic has led to an increase in electricity generation. In 2023, the power stations of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic produced 474,569,561 kWh of electricity, which is 6,252,667 kWh or 1.3% more than in 2022 [5]. Currently, there are 2 thermal power plants, 5 hydroelectric power plants, 3 solar power plants, 1 hybrid wind-solar power plant, and 1 wind power plant in operation in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The construction of the 32 MW diversion-type Ordubad Hydroelectric Power Plant and the 15.6 MW diversion-type Tivi Hydroelectric Power Plant on the Araz River is ongoing. The "State Program for the Socio-Economic Development of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic for 2023-2027" includes plans for the development of alternative and renewable energy sources, the implementation of new energy projects through public-private partnerships, and the construction of new thermal power plants. **Conclusion** In the modern era, the efforts made to ensure energy security in our country are yielding results. Specifically, during the 10 years from 2013 to 2023, electricity production in the Republic of Azerbaijan increased by 7.5%, from 23,354.4 million kWh in 2013 to 29,305.9 million kWh in 2023. During this period, electricity production in hydropower plants increased by 3.3%, from 1,489.1 million kWh to 1,763.4 million kWh, in wind power plants by 68.3 times, from 0.8 million kWh to 55.4 million kWh, in solar power plants by 100.9 times, from 0.8 million kWh to 80.7 million kWh, and electricity generation from waste incineration increased by 14.8%, from 134.1 million kWh to 223.0 million kWh. Azerbaijan has a geographically advantageous "green energy" potential. A targeted state policy is being pursued to efficiently utilize this potential. The implementation of "green energy" projects will further enhance their significance and role in strengthening the sustainable development of the economy.

References

1. Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, <https://www.economy.gov.az>
2. State Agency on Renewable Energy Sources under the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, <https://area.gov.az>
3. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, <https://www.stat.gov.az>
4. Nagiev K.Z. "The role and significance of sustainable development in the change of the population in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic," International Scientific and Practical Conference Materials, Baku, October 4, 2024, pp. 344-348
5. Nakhchivan MR State Energy Service, <https://nminenergy.gov.az>